

HETEROGENEOUS REACTION BETWEEN CHROMIC SULPHATE AND MANGANESE DIOXIDE.

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The velocity of the heterogeneous reaction between finely divided powdered manganese dioxide and chromium sulphate solution has been studied. The reaction is concluded to be analogous to the decomposition of ammonia.

Prasad, Naqvi and Shetgiri (*Current Sci.*, 1939, 8, 361) have shown that when a solution of chromium sulphate is shaken with solid hydrated manganese dioxide, dichromate ions are formed in the solution. According to them the reaction takes place as

The correctness of the above equation has been established by them by performing several quantitative experiments.

The present investigation deals with the velocity of the heterogeneous reaction between finely powdered manganese dioxide and a solution of chromium sulphate.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Hydrated manganese dioxide was prepared by the method described by Chatterjee (*Chem. News*, 1921, 123, 232). A solution of Merck's pure manganese sulphate containing a small quantity of potassium nitrate was gently heated and a solution of potassium permanganate was added to it drop by drop, with constant stirring, until the supernatant liquid was distinctly pink. The precipitated manganese dioxide was washed free from impurities and then dried at about 50°. On analysis the oxide gave moisture, 13.75%; Mn, 54.94%; O₂, 31.31% (Mn : O = 1 : 1.969).

This was passed through sieves of different meshes and various fractions between two sieves were collected and carefully stored.

Solution of chromium sulphate was prepared from Merck's pure substance and its concentration was determined in terms of dichromate formed by oxidising it with sodium peroxide. Solutions of different concentrations were prepared from this stock solution by diluting it suitably.

The sieved dioxide (0.25 g.) was taken in each of the seven conical flasks and 50 c.c. of the chromium sulphate solution were added to each.

The flasks were then shaken on a shaking machine placed in the thermostat, maintained at a constant temperature. The flasks were removed separately at known intervals of time and the solutions were immediately filtered. Several trials showed that the effective filtration can be quickly carried out through filter papers coated with a thin layer of collodion. The filtrate was then made up to 100 c.c. and the dichromate formed was estimated by titrating it against a standard solution of the ferrous ammonium sulphate, using diphenylamine as the indicator.

The results in Table I show that the presence of chromium sulphate does not affect the estimation of dichromate ions by the method mentioned above. It will be noticed that the mixtures chosen contain very large proportions of chromium sulphate as it happens in actual experiments.

TABLE I.

10 C.c. of the $K_2Cr_2O_7$ solution \equiv 9.5 c.c. of a solution of ferrous am. sulphate.

Mixtures		Ferrous ammonium sulphate.	
$K_2Cr_2O_7$.	$Cr_2(SO_4)_3$.	Reqd.	Calc.
6 c.c.	44 c.c.	5.65 c.c.	5.70 c.c.
4	46	3.80	3.80
2	48	1.90	1.90
1	49	0.95	0.95

The results obtained are given in the following tables in which C represents the concentration of chromium sulphate solution in the form mentioned above; y , the equivalents of dichromate ions formed at various intervals and T , the temperature at which the reaction was carried out.

TABLE II.

Particles between 60 and 80 mesh.

Time.	Equivalents of dichromate ions formed			
	$(C = 61.6 \times 10^{-4} N)$		$(C = 154.0 \times 10^{-4} N)$	
	$T = 46^\circ$	$T = 36^\circ$	$T = 46^\circ$	$T = 36^\circ$
2 min.	6.05×10^{-4}	4.29×10^{-4}	8.53×10^{-4}	5.90×10^{-4}
5	8.25	5.89	10.45	7.50
10	10.45	6.97	12.10	9.11
20	11.55	7.77	14.03	9.91
30	11.83	8.31	14.58	10.45
40	12.93	9.38	15.13	10.99
60	14.58	10.18	15.95	11.80

TABLE III.

Particles between 80 and 100 mesh.

Time.	Equivalents of dichromate ions formed.		
	$C = 61.6 \times 10^{-4} N$		
	$T = 46^\circ.$	$T = 36^\circ.$	$T = 46^\circ.$
2 min.	7.15×10^{-4}	4.95×10^{-4}	10.45×10^{-4}
5	8.80	6.88	12.38
10	11.00	7.98	13.48
20	13.20	9.63	15.13
30	13.75	10.73	15.68
40	14.58	11.00	16.23
60	15.68	11.53	17.33

DISCUSSION.

It will be seen that the reaction between chromic sulphate and manganese dioxide is very rapid in the beginning but slows down within a short time. Tables I and II give the effects of (i) the change in concentration of chromium sulphate, (ii) the size of the particles, roughly indicated by the size of the sieves through which the manganese dioxide has been sieved, and (iii) the temperature on the reaction. It will be seen that increasing amounts of dichromate ions are formed as (a) the concentration of the chromic sulphate solution, (b) the size of the particles, and (c) the temperature at which the reaction is carried out, are increased.

Nernst (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1904, **47**, 52) has shown on certain assumptions that the order of heterogeneous reactions which proceed fairly rapidly is unimolecular. This conclusion has been verified mainly in dissolution reactions (*cf.* Von Name, *Amer. J. Sci.*, 1917, **43**, 453; King and Braverman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 1744; Collenberg and Bodfross, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1921, **101**, 117). Attempts made to determine the order of the reaction studied in this investigation showed that it is not a unimolecular one.

The heterogeneous reactions take place owing to the adsorption of the molecules of the reactant at the surface of a solid. The rate of this reaction is retarded if the molecules of the product or products formed in the reaction are also adsorbed by the solid. In the heterogeneous reactions at the gas-solid interface, if the adsorption of the reacting gas is smaller

than the adsorption of the gaseous product, the rate of reaction is given by

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{k(a-x)}{1+bx}$$

where k and b are constants. The integrated form of this expression is

$$v = \left(a + \frac{1}{b} \right) k_m - \frac{k}{b} \quad \dots (1)$$

where $v = \frac{x}{t}$ and $k_m = \frac{2.3}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x}$

Hinshelwood and Prichard (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 327) found that the above expression is applicable to the catalytic decomposition of nitrous oxide at the surface of platinum. On plotting v against k_m they found that the curve is a straight line which cuts the axis of v on the negative side and the slope of the line is given by $\left(a + \frac{1}{b} \right)$.

If the adsorption of the gaseous product is very great then the reaction velocity is given by

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{k(a-x)}{x}$$

which, on integration, gives

$$v = ak_m - k. \quad \dots (2)$$

The application of this expression has been realised by Hinshelwood and Burk (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1114) in the decomposition of ammonia on the surface of heated platinum wire in the region of 1000°.

FIG. 1.

The application of the expressions (1) and (2) was examined in the case of the reaction between chromium sulphate and manganese dioxide. Values of v are plotted against k_m and the straight lines obtained are shown in Fig 1. It will be seen that the straight lines intersect the v -axis on the negative side but the values of the intercepts are very small. Also points corresponding to the reaction at different temperatures with the solution of chromium sulphate of the same concentration and of different particle size, lie on the same straight line. Values of the slopes S of the two lines shown in the figure are nearly the same as the concentration C of the chromium sulphate solution. This leads to the conclusion that the reaction studied in this investigation is analogous to the decomposition of ammonia and that the rate of this reaction is governed by the expression (2).

Further work on the subject is in progress.

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